

Isatin : A versatile molecule for the synthesis of novel spiroheterocycles[†]

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Several new spiroheterocycles synthesized in the author's laboratory, starting from appropriately substituted isatins have been briefly described.

Isatin (1), also known as indole-2,3-dione, can be considered to be the *o*-quinone of 2,3-dihydroxyindole. It is a unique molecule possessing both amide and ketocarbonyl groups. Apart from this, it has an active hydrogen atom attached to nitrogen (or oxygen) and an aromatic ring which should substitute at 5- and 7-positions. It exists in a tautomeric form (2) and these functional characteristics play an important role in governing the various reactions of the molecule.

The C-3 carbonyl group of isatin is strongly electrophilic. As a result, isatins are readily involved in condensation and addition reactions with carbanion type nucleophiles into 3-substituted oxindoles¹. However, a number of reports indicate the involvement of both the carbonyl groups during the reaction. In general, there are three possibilities during condensation reactions : (i) both the α,β -carbonyl groups, having varying reactivity, are involved, (ii) ring cleavage takes place and (iii) ring expansion occurs. A general observation has been that the nature of the final product always depends on the experimental conditions and substituents at nitrogen atom which may affect the electron density at α - and β -carbonyl carbon atom respectively².

Indoles with C-3 as spiro atom

Many of the above reactions lead to the synthesis of spiroindoles, with C-3 as spiro atom and have received considerable attention in recent times³. The C-3 atom of the indole ring is shared by another ring and therefore leads to a variety of heterocyclic systems attached at C-3 of the indole ring. Considerable interest is attached to these compounds for various reasons. (i) There are numerous possibilities of synthesizing new heterocyclic systems with interesting stereochemical features. (ii) There are various indole alkaloids with a C-3 spiro atom and can be synthesized from

substituted isatins. (iii) During some cyclization and rearrangement reactions, unexpected formation of spiroindoles is observed. (iv) The other ring incorporated at C-3 can have wide variations. We have been able to incorporate various kinds of rings beginning from a one-ring system (with or without a heteroatom) like cyclopropane to three-ring systems with heteroatom and have reported some very interesting new ring systems — a few of which are being reviewed here.

Majority of such compounds have a fluorine substituent at an appropriate site. Introduction of fluorine into the indole nucleus is believed to increase drug persistence by increasing its solubility in lipid material and fat deposits in body⁴. The chemotherapeutic importance of fluorinated isatin derivatives is well established⁵.

With this background, we have exploited appropriately substituted isatins for synthesizing several new heterocyclic systems which were reported for the first time. In the following pages, a brief review of our work in the field of such spiroheterocycles is being given.

Spiro[indole-thiazolidine]ones

This system was extensively investigated due to (i) broad spectrum of biological activities, (ii) presence of different reaction sites (C=O, NH and CH₂) and (iii) non-availability of spectral data. Further, there were only two references in the literature, one being a patent and the other did not report the yields.

The synthesis of spiro[3*H*-indole-3,2'-thiazolidine]-2,4' (1*H*)-diones (3) was carried out by the condensation of isatin-3-anils with mercaptoacetic acid. The compounds have also been directly obtained from isatins, amines and mercaptoacetic acid without the isolation of isatin-3-anils. The compounds have successfully undergone acetylation, chloroacetylation and Mannich reaction⁶⁻⁸.

Reaction of fluorinated 3-arylimine-2*H*-indol-2-ones (4) with mercaptoacetic acid was also investigated under dif-

[†] Dedicated to Professor D. Nasipuri on his 75th. birth anniversary.

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X = F, CF₃
 Ar = Subs phenyl
 R = H, alkyl, acyl, morpholinomethyl

Y = 2-F, 4-F, 3-CH₃
 R = H, CH₃

R = H, CH₃
 X = 5-F, 6-F, 4-CF₃
 Y = 2-F, 4-F, 3-CH₃, 2,5-diF

ferent reaction conditions, such as temperature, reaction period and molar ratio of the two reactants. Reaction of **4** with mercaptoacetic yields the spiro derivative when taken in 1 : 1.5 molar ratio and refluxed for 2 h. The reaction of **4** with mercaptoacetic acid at room temperature in 1 : 3 molar ratio also results in the formation of the spiro derivative in 10 h⁹.

R = H, CH₃
 R¹ = H, 5-F, 4-CF₃
 R² = 3-Cl, 4-F

Spiro[indole-pyrazole]ones

The spiro[indole-pyrazoline] nucleus has attracted the attention in view of its analgesic and antiphlogistic properties and its use as blood platelet aggregators. Earlier, not much attention was paid to the reaction of **5** with various hydrazine derivatives such as phenylhydrazine and pentafluoro-phenylhydrazine. Further, there is some controversy about the formation of products during this reaction. Kobayashi and Furukawa¹⁰ and Ocomasu *et al*¹¹ reported different products in different media. The reaction was, therefore, reinvestigated.

Spiro[3H-indole-3,3'-(3H)pyrazol]-2(1H)-ones (**6**) were obtained by the condensation of hydrazine hydrate with equimolar amount of 3-arylmethyleneindol-2-ones (**5**). The latter were prepared by dehydration of 3-hydroxy-3-phenacylindol-2-ones which were obtained by the reaction of indole-2,3-diones and acetophenone. Most of these had fluorine substituents¹².

Reaction of **5** (R = H) with phenylhydrazine afforded a mixture of the corresponding spiro derivative along with a condensed and hydrazine derivative with variations in yield in absolute ethanol and glacial acetic acid, while that of **5** (R = CH₃) gave the spiro compound exclusively in 95% yield¹³. Various substitution reactions¹⁴, viz. methylation

and hydroxymethylation of spiro[3H-indol-3,3-[3H]pyrazol]-2(1H)-ones (**6**) were studied and position of substituent assigned. In all these reactions, substitution occurred preferably at pyrazolyl nitrogen (**7**). Further, conversion of the spiro compounds into the corresponding thiones (**8**) was carried out using P₂S₅ and this type of conversion is not reported in such systems earlier.

R¹ = H, Cl
 R² = H, 4-F, 2,5-diCl, 3-Cl-4F
 X = H, C₆H₅

Spiro[indoline-pyrazolopyridines]

The pyridoindole nucleus, known as a carboline system, is the parent skeleton of several alkaloids and biologically active compounds. When the pyrazolone skeleton is incorporated into the former nucleus, some interesting reactions take place.

The reactions of 3-aminopyrazolone with 3-(2-oxoethylidene)indole-2-ones were investigated in view of the fact that the latter can undergo reactions involving either the double bond and lactam carbonyl group or α,β -unsaturated carbonyl group of the side-chain or it can undergo condensation involving both the carbonyl groups.

The reaction of fluorinated 1,3-dihydro-3-(2-phenyl-2-oxoethylidene)indole-2(H)-ones with 3-amino-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one in absolute ethanol gave **9**. On prolonged refluxing **10** was obtained. They were identified as 2',3',3'a,5'-tetrahydro-5-fluoro-6'-(4-fluorophenyl)-2'-phenylspiro[indoline-3,4'-pyrazolo[3,4-b]pyridine]-2,3'-dione and 2',3',3'a,7'-tetrahydro-4'-(4-fluorophenyl)-2'-phenylspiro[indoline-3,6'[6H]pyrazolo[3,4-b]pyridine]-2,3'-dione, respectively¹⁵.

Spiro[pyrano[2,3-c]pyrazoles]

Spiro[3*H*-indole-3,4'(1*H*)-pyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazole]-5'-carbonitriles/carboxyethyl esters (**11**) were prepared by the reaction of 3-(cyanomethylene)oxindole with 3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone in piperidine in EtOH¹⁶. These compounds exhibited herbicidal activity.

R¹ = H, MeCO₂, morpholinomethyl, piperidinomethyl
R² = H, F, CF₃, R³ = CN, CO₂Et

Spiro[pyrazolo[3,4-c]pyrazoles]

The reaction of F-containing indolones with phenylhydrazine in absolute ethanol gave only spiro compounds (**12**), but mixtures of spiro and fused tetracyclic products were obtained when hydrazine hydrate was used instead of phenylhydrazine¹⁷.

X = 5-F, 6-F
R¹ = H, -COCH₃
R² = H, C₆H₅

Spiro[dipyrazolo[3,4-b, 4,3-c]pyran]

Spiro[dipyrazolo[3,4-*b*, 4,3-*e*]pyran-4-(4*H*)-3'-3(*H*)-indole]-2'(1'*H*)-ones (**13**) were prepared by reaction of isatin with pyrazolone in the molar ratio 1 : 2 in refluxing ethanol^{18,19}.

Spiro[indole-pyrimidines]

The reaction of 3-arylmethylene indoline-2-ones with thiosemicarbazide is found to be dependent on substitution of 'N' atom. While unsubstituted 'N' gives exclusively the hydrazone, the *N*-methyl-3-arylmethyleneindoline-2-ones, under exactly similar conditions, afforded a spiro[indole-

pyrimidine] derivative (**14**). Thus, spiro[3*H*-indole-3,4'(3'*H*)-pyrimidine-2(1*H*)-ones (**14**) were synthesized by the reaction of *N*-methyl-3-arylmethyleneindoline-2-ones (R = CH₃) with thiosemicarbazide²⁰.

R = H, CH₃
R¹ = C₆H₅, 3-CH₃C₆H₃4F

3-Arylmethyleneindol-2-ones when reacted with phenylthiourea²¹, gave spiro[3*H*-indole-3,4'(3'*H*)-pyrimidin]-2(1*H*)one (**15**).

Spiro[indole-thiazines]

When we started investigating this system²², having a thiazine ring incorporated into it, there was only one report in the literature and that too being a patent. While publishing this work, a paper by Rajopadhye and Popp²³ appeared, confirming our results. This is a novel spiro heterocycle bearing an indoline and a thiazine moiety and has different reaction sites (>C=O, >NH, -CO-CH₂ and -S-CH₂-) thus leading to many reactions like acetylation, chloroacetylation and Mannich reactions.

Spiro[3*H*-indole-3,2'-terahydro-1,3-thiazine]-2,4'-(1*H*)-dione (**16**) was synthesized by a one step procedure involving the condensation of fluorine containing indole-2,3-diones, fluorinated aromatic amines and 3-mercapto propanoic acid without isolating the intermediate isatin-3-anils. *N*-Acetylated spiro compound was simultaneously synthesized from 1-acetyl indole-2,3-dione and aniline.

Spiro [indole-isoxazoles]

Spiro[3*H*-indole-3,5'-isoxazolin]-2(1*H*)-ones (**17**) were prepared by the reaction of 3-arylmethyleneindole-2-ones with hydroxylamine hydrochloride. The spiro derivative showed antibacterial and antifungal activities²⁴.

Spiro[indole-oxiranes]

Epoxidation of 3-arylmethyleneindole-2-ones with hydrogen peroxide was earlier reported to give spiro[3*H*-indole-3,2'-oxiran]-2(*H*)-ones. These reports were patents and gave no details. Theoretically, it appeared that such compounds could exist in the form of two isomers differing in the stereochemical arrangement of the hydrogen atom of the oxirane ring. During the course of this investigation²⁵, the product was found to be a mixture of two compounds in the ratio of 1 : 1.

Reaction of 3-arylmethyleneindole-2-ones with H₂O₂ resulted in the formation of a 1 : 1 isomeric mixture of spiro[3*H*-indole-3,2'-oxiran]-2(1*H*)-ones (**18,19**) which gave identical mass spectrum, although in the PMR, the peak due to CH was at a slightly different position.

Spiro[benzopyran-indoles]

3-Dicyano/carboethoxycyanomethyleneindole-2-ones when subjected to Michael reaction with cyclohexane-1,3-

diones²⁶, gave spiro[4*H*-1-benzopyran-4,3'-[3*H*]-indol]-3-carbonitriles/carboxyethylesters (**20**).

These compounds are of interest as insecticides. The spiro[benzopyran-2,2'-indoles] are used for photochromatic effect.

Spiro[benzothiazine-indoles]

In this system, a benzothiazine moiety has been incorporated. Spiro[2*H*-1,3-benzothiazine-2,3'-[3*H*]-indole]2',4(1'*H*,3*H*)-diones (**21**) were prepared by the cyclocondensation of 3-arylimino-2*H*-indol-2-ones with *o*-mercaptobenzoic acid in acidic ethanol. The spiro compound was further subjected to methylation and morphomethylation^{27,28}.

Spiro[benzothiazole]-2(3*H*)-3'-indol]-2'(1'*H*)-one (**22**) was synthesized by the reaction of 1-methylindole-2,3-dione with 2-aminothiophenol in dry xylene in the presence of anhydrous ZnCl₂²⁹. This reaction was reinvestigated by us and some interesting results, at variance from earlier reports, were obtained.

Spiro[indole-tetrazine]thiones

A novel system, 2-oxo-1',2',4',5'-tetrahydrospiro[3*H*-indole-3,3'-1,2,4,5-tetrazine]-6'-thione (**23**) was prepared by the treatment of fluorinated isatin with thiocarbohydrazide in aqueous ethanolic medium. Under exactly similar conditions, *N*-acetylisatin gave exclusively the thiocarbohydrazone³⁰.

X = 5-F, 6-F

Spiro[acridine-indoles]

A new spiroheterocyclic system, spiro[9*H*-acridine-9,3'-[3*H*]-indol]-2'(1*H*)-ones (**24**) was prepared by the reaction of spiro[3*H*-indole-3,9'-[9*H*]xanthen]-2(1*H*)-ones (**25**) with aromatic amine or ammonium acetate. The latter were prepared by heating fluorinated indole-2,3-diones with *m/p*-cresols or α -naphthol in the presence of sulphuric acid at 230–240°³¹.

X = 5-F, 6-F, 4-CF₃

Y = 2,7-diCH₃, 3,6-diCH₃, 2,7-diF

Z = H, 4-F

R = H, CH₃COCH₃, COC₆H₅

25

Spiro[3*H*-indole-3,9'(9*H*)-xanthen]-1',2',8'-(1*H*)-2'*H*,5'*H*)-triones (**26**) were prepared by irradiating indole-2,3-diones with 1,3-cyclohexanedione in excess of glacial acetic acid^{32,33}.

R = 5-F, 6-F

R¹ = H, Ac X = O

Spiro[azetidine-indoles]

While studying the role of fluoroaryl groups in

cyclocondensation reactions with mercaptoacetic acid and with chloroacetyl chloride, it was observed that the course of the reaction differs when pentafluoroaryl groups is present.

Spiro[azetidine-2,3'-3*H*-indole]-2',4(1*H*)-dione (**28**) was obtained by the reaction of anil **27** (Ar = 2,3,4,5,6-C₆HF₄) with ClCH₂COCl⁷. These compounds were screened for antibacterial activity. It was noticed that the incorporation of fluorine in a compound increases the antibacterial activity against both gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria.

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28

Spiro[indole-pyrano]2,3-*d*]pyrimidines

Spiro[3*H*-indole-3,5'-[5*H*]pyrano[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines]-6'-carbonitriles (**29**) were prepared by the Michael reaction of 3-dicyano- and carboethoxycyanomethylene-2-oxindoles with phenylbarbituric acid³⁴.

29

R = H, 5-F, 6-F, 4-CF₃

R¹ = H, Me morpholinomethyl

R² = CN, CO₂Et

Similarly, fluorinated spiro[3*H*-indole-3,4'(4*H*)-pyrano[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine]-2,5',7'(1*H*)-triones (**30**) were synthesized by the Michael reaction of 3-(carboethoxycyano/dicyano)methyleneindole-2-ones with barbituric acid, the former being obtained from indole-2,3-dione and malononitrile/ethyl cyanoacetate³⁵.

30

X = 5-F, 6-F, 4-CF₃

R = H, COCH₃ CH₂N

R¹ = CN, CO₂C₂H₅

Spiro[indole-pyrazolo[3,2-d][1,3,5]thiadiazepines

Reaction of mercaptoacetic acid with fluorinated 3-aryliminoindole-2-ones prepared *in situ* from fluorinated indole-2,3-diones and fluorinated anilines, yielded 3'-arylspiro[3*H*-indole-3,2'-thiazolidine]-2(1*H*)-diones. Under similar conditions, 3-(4-phenylpyrazol-5-ylimino)indol-2-ones yielded a novel system 4',5'-dihydro-9'-phenylspiro-[3*H*-indole-3,2'(1'*H*)-pyrazolo[3,2-*d*][1,3,5]thiadiazepine]-2(1*H*)5'-dione (31). 3-(4-Phenylpyrazol-5-ylimino)indol-2-ones have been synthesized by the reaction of fluoroine-containing indole-2,3-diones with 3-amino-4-phenylpyrazole in absolute ethanol³⁶.

Spiro[benzimidazole-indoles]

Reactions of indole-2,3-diones with 1,2-phenylenediamine and 2,3-diaminopyridine in different media led to different products with change of media. 1,3-Dihydro-spiro[2*H*-benzimidazole-2,3'-[3*H*]indol]-2'(1*H*)-ones (33) were the main products formed by the reaction of 1-acetylindole-2,3-dione with 1,2-phenylenediamines (32) in both glacial acetic acid and ethanol³⁷.

Spiro[triazolo[5,1-b]quinazolines]

Spiro[3*H*-indole-3,2'(1'*H*)-[1,2,4]triazolo[5,1-*b*]quinazoline]-2,9'(1*H*,3'*H*)-diones (34) were prepared by the reaction of fluorinated isatin derivatives with 2,3-diamino-4(3*H*)-quinazolone in ethanolic KOH. The Schiff base 2-amino-3-(1,2-dihydro-2-oxo-3*H*-indol-3-ylideneamino)-4(3*H*)-quinazolinone (35) was isolated only in the case of reaction with 5-fluoroisatin in glacial acetic acid³⁸.

Spiro[indole-pyranobenzopyrans] and spiro[indenopyran-indoles]

An elegant one-step synthesis of two novel spiro ring systems, viz. spiro[3*H*-indole-3,4'-(2'-amino-3'-carboni-

trile-(4'*H*)-pyrano[3,2-*c*]benzopyran]-2,5'(1*H*)-diones (36) and spiro[(2-amino-3-carbonitrite-indino[1,2-*b*]pyran)-4(5*H*), 3'-[3*H*]indole]-2',5(1'*H*)-diones (37) was done. The spiro heterocycles were prepared by the reactions of fluoroine containing 3-dicyanomethylene-2*H*-indol-2-ones with 4-hydroxy-2*H*-1-benzopyran-2-one and 1*H*-indene-1,3(2*H*)-dione respectively³⁹.

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